

Appendices

Appendix 1 Ethogram of the observed activities in the experimental setup.

Behaviour	Category	Description	Behaviour	Category	Description
Standing	Position	<i>The animal is standing still, all four limbs are on the ground. Occasionally, one limb may be raised, and the animal occasionally moves its head.</i>	Kicked	Social	<i>The animal is targeted by another animal. It receives a headbutt to its head or another part of the body.</i>
Walking	Position	<i>At least two limbs are in motion.</i>	Fighting	Social	<i>The animal fights with another individual. The animal headbutts the head or body of the other animal. The animal may rise on its hind legs and then fall back before headbutting another individual.</i>
Lying down	Position	<i>The goat first places its two front legs, knees on the ground, then the hindquarters fall down.</i>	Allogrooming	Social	<i>The animal's muzzle makes contact with the body of another animal.</i>
Lying	Position	<i>The animal is lying down and still, occasionally moving its head.</i>	Other social interaction	Social	<i>Social interaction not mentioned above.</i>
Standing up	Position	<i>The goat positions itself on its knees, forearms on the ground, and then lifts its hindquarters to stand up.</i>	None	Social	<i>No social interaction.</i>
Climbing	Position	<i>The goat places its front legs on a surface or an object.</i>	Shaking	Other	<i>The animal shakes its entire body vigorously and then often briefly shakes its head as a second step.</i>
Milking	Position	<i>The animal has left the pen to go for milking.</i>	Head shaking	Other	<i>The animal shakes its head only.</i>
Other position	Position	<i>Position or movement not mentioned above.</i>	Rubbing	Other	<i>The animal rubs its body against the barrier and moves forward while continuing to press its body against it.</i>
Non-visible	Position	<i>The movement/position of the animal cannot be determined with certainty or is not visible, incomplete...</i>	Chewing	Other	<i>Nibbles on something (anything that is not food or another goat).</i>
Head in the feeder	Feeding	<i>The animal opens its gate by placing its head in it.</i>	Grooming	Other	<i>The animal scratches or licks itself.</i>
Drinking	Feeding	<i>The animal has its muzzle in the water trough.</i>	Scratching	Other	<i>The goat uses one of its hind legs to scratch the front part of its body.</i>
Ruminating	Feeding	<i>The animal chews for a while. The regular jaw movements accompanied by ear movement can be observed, periodically interrupted by the swallowing of the bolus.</i>	Other behaviour	Other	<i>Other behaviour not mentioned above.</i>
Salt block	Feeding	<i>The animal licks the salt block.</i>	None	Other	<i>No other behaviour.</i>
None	Feeding	<i>The animal is not eating, does not have its muzzle in the water trough, and is not ruminating.</i>	None	Other	<i>No other behaviour.</i>
Other feeding behaviour	Feeding	<i>Feeding behaviour not mentioned above.</i>	Disturbance yes	Disturbance	<i>An unexpected/abnormal event occurs; an individual enters the device, noise, camera obstructed...</i>
			No disturbance	Disturbance	<i>Nothing abnormal/unexpected to report.</i>

Appendix 2 Confusion matrix (a) and performance model evaluation metrics (b)

(a)

	Positive	Negative
Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
Negative	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

(b)

Metric	Formula
Accuracy	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$
Sensitivity (recall)	$\frac{TP}{FN + TP}$
Specificity	$\frac{TN}{TN + FP}$
Balanced accuracy	$\frac{(sensitivity + specificity)}{2}$
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
F1-score	$2 * \frac{recall * precision}{recall + precision}$
AUC score	Area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve

Appendix 3 Classification performance for “head in the feeder” using the Catboost algorithm with different selected time-window sizes (i), cut-off frequencies (ii), additional time-series (iii), numbers of selected features (iv).

Time-window sizes (s)	10	20	30	40	50	60	80	120		
AUC score	0.772	0.779	0.775	0.779	0.784	0.819	0.770	0.773		
Cut-off frequencies (Hz)	No filtering	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4			
AUC score	0.819	0.746	0.784	0.782	0.775	0.785	0.793			
Additional time-series	None	Euler angles	Rotated acc data (mean)	Rotated acc data (median)	Rotated acc data (mean) + Euler angles	Rotated acc data (median) + Euler angles				
AUC score	0.797	0.795	0.815	0.775	0.819	0.774				
Number of the best features selected	6993 (no selection)	2000	1000	500	100	80	50	20	10	
AUC score		0.816	0.817	0.819	0.818	0.818	0.819	0.817	0.808	0.792

Appendix 4 Classification performance for “lying” using the Catboost algorithm with different selected time-window sizes (i), cut-off frequencies (ii), additional time-series (iii), numbers of selected features (iv).

Time-window sizes (s)	10	20	30	40	50	60	80	120
AUC score	0.809	0.789	0.780	0.787	0.829	0.817	0.801	0.775

Cut-off frequencies (Hz)	No filtering	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
AUC score	0.829	0.764	0.767	0.774	0.782	0.776	0.803

Additional time-series	None	Euler angles	Rotated acc data (mean)	Rotated acc data (median)	Rotated acc data (mean) + Euler angles	Rotated acc data (median) + Euler angles
AUC score	0.829	0.764	0.784	0.792	0.829	0.790

Number of the best features selected	6993 (no feature selection)	2000	1000	500	100	80	50	20	10
AUC score	0.822	0.822	0.826	0.826	0.825	0.829	0.823	0.811	0.810

Appendix 5 Classification performance for “standing” using the Catboost algorithm with different selected time-window sizes (i), cut-off frequencies (ii), additional time-series (iii), numbers of selected features (iv).

Time-window sizes (s)	10	20	30	40	50	60	80	120
AUC score	0.790	0.799	0.820	0.774	0.804	0.823	0.802	0.801

Cut-off frequencies (Hz)	No filtering	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
AUC score	0.823	0.808	0.797	0.772	0.780	0.792	0.798

Additional time-series	None	Euler angles	Rotated acc data (mean)	Rotated acc data (median)	Rotated acc data (mean) + Euler angles	Rotated acc data (median) + Euler angles
AUC score	0.819	0.823	0.815	0.766	0.819	0.776

Number of the best features selected	4662 (no feature selection)	2000	1000	500	100	80	50	20
AUC score	0.819	0.818	0.819	0.819	0.819	0.820	0.816	0.801

Appendix 6 Permutation entropy calculated on the norm distribution during non-lying (0) and lying events (1)

